

QoL-18

Please complete the survey below.

Thank you!

Please answer the following questions to the best of your ability for each of the topics listed below.

Compared to 4 weeks ago, before you and your loved one started using the MapHabit System, please reflect and assess if and to what degree your loved one may have experienced changes (improvements, regression, or no change) in the following areas:

	1 = Much negative change	2 = Some negative change	3 = No change	4 = Some positive change	5 = Much positive change
1) Mood	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
2) Independence	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
3) Ability to carry out some activities of daily living	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
4) Completion of activities of daily living more quickly	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
5) Needing reminders during an activity of daily living	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
6) Social Interaction	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
7) Depression	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
8) Anxiety	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
9) Frustration	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
10) Anger	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
11) Coping Ability	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
12) Memory	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
13) Social engagement	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
14) Overall quality of life	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
15) Enjoyment of life	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
16) Positive Moments	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
17) Expression of appreciation	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
18) Cooperation	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

SS-2

How satisfied are you with your progress in this program?					
	Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral/Did Not Use	Not Very Satisfied	Very Dissatisfied
How satisfied are you with your progress in this program?	☐				

How likely is it that you would recommend the MapHabit System to a friend or colleague?					
	Extremely	Very Likely	Neutral	Unlikely	Extremely Unlikely
How likely is it that you would recommend the MapHabit System to a friend or colleague?	☐				